

Biological ageing determined by statistical constraints: a hypothesis on mortality

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Abstract

This article presents a conjecture, based on recent research carried out by the author, concerning ageing and consequent demographic mortality. This conjecture hypothesizes that all human populations will show a demographic mortality trend as longevity increases. In particular, the demographic mortality curve will tend to converge towards a defined theoretical curve. This curve is calculated mathematically using an abstract model of cellular automata and a method based on Fermi statistics. This automaton (which we call the Arbitrary Oscillator) is constrained to end its life cycle upon reaching a maximum number of paths defined by a parameter TC (Total Counts). In the study, we highlight the mathematical properties of the curve and compare it with the trend of real mortality curves for various populations and for various historical periods. In doing so, we use the Life Tables generated by the demographic institutes of various countries. From this comparison, it appears that the conjecture may be reasonable and an attempt to predict demographic mortality behavior and limitations for the years to come is provided. From the mathematical properties of the theoretical distribution, constraints on the future development of mortality curves can also be deduced, should the conjecture be confirmed. In this case, the mortality curve cannot exceed a certain level of maximum peak height nor fall below a minimum width at half the height of the same peak. Another typical feature of real mortality distribution curves is that they are asymmetrical, with a tail of data to the left of the maximum peak. Using the explicit function, we show how this asymmetry can be interpreted as due to the sum of several discrete sub-components within the overall distribution. A discussion is held on the nature of these possible sub-components that appear at discrete age clusters. The availability of a mathematical description of the mortality distribution also allows us to compare the model with the experimental Gompertz law, finding confirmation of it except at high ages, where our model predicts a saturation. In this article, we also consider the possibility of extending these models to species other than humans by defining a species 'time constant'. In the conclusions, the more general theme of the nature of biologic ageing is seen in connection to our conjecture that predicts the presence of an absolute limit (linked to the TC parameter) on the number of 'critical' events. As 'critical' events accumulate over time by ageing, approaching the final limit value, the probability of death will tend toward one as a result of a sort of statistical "pressure". Finally, we hypothesize a conceptual link between the TC parameter of the theoretical distribution and the Intrinsic Capacity (IC) parameter defined by the World Health Organisation.

Key Words: Demographic Mortality, Cellular Automata, Statistical Mechanics, Ergodic Hypothesis, Statistical Distributions, Demographic Life Tables, Biological Clock, Gompertz Law, Ageing, Fermi time, Intrinsic Capacity.

1. Introduction

The inevitability of the end of life has always captured the human imagination, giving rise to multiple interpretations of a moral, religious and, of course, social nature in all cultures and populations. Artists, too, have been struck by this, highlighting – through paintings, plays or literary works – how this immutable law applies to all human beings, regardless of their wealth or position of power. In our study, however, we wish to focus, more modestly, on the statistical characteristics of demographic mortality. The literature on demographic mortality is enormous and covers a broad spectrum of scientific and social aspects. It is beyond the scope and capacity of this article to attempt to review and make reference to these studies. We will therefore only refer to works strictly instrumental to the contents of this work, leaving the correlation with other studies on the topic to the interest and experience of the reader. For our analysis, we will use the data provided by demographic monitoring institutions in various countries. In particular, the mortality data collected in the so-called Life Tables will be useful. To get an idea of how this data can be used, let's look at Figure 1.

Fig. 1 - Number (l_x) of survivors from a set of 100000 newborns as the age increases

In this Figure, we consider a hypothetical group of 100,000 newborns who progressively age from the moment of their birth. We can see that as the years pass, the number (called l_x) of members in the group decreases until it disappears once their age exceeds a certain maximum limit called lifespan. A striking feature of this survival curve is that during the initial phase of youth and even during a period of relative maturity, there is no significant decline in the number of members in the group. However, at a certain point, something “goes wrong” and suddenly the number of survivors decreases until the entire population group disappears. This process of 'decay' is typical of many living beings and not only of the human species. In Figure 2, whose trend is typical for all countries, we have used mortality data from 2019 (before the impact of the COVID pandemic), grouped into 5-year intervals (Figure dots), for females in Japan, Ref [1]. It may be interesting to compare this process with other inanimate processes found in nature. Take, for example, radioactive decay, in which isotopes of a certain element decay according to the well-known exponential law. This second 'mortality' curve is also shown in Figure 1. For the comparison, we assumed that the radioactive source has a time constant such that its half-life coincides with that of our demographic group. It can be seen that, in the case of the radioactive source, the decay does not show rapid variations but continues with an exponential decrease without any apparent lifespan limit. There is no “ageing” in the atomic world. I.e., the probability of decay of an atom is independent of the age of the atom. Ref. [2]. These differences are even more evident in Figure 2, which shows deaths per 5-year interval as the age of the group changes.

Fig. 2 - No. of deaths (dx) in a 5-years age interval as the newborn group age increases

It can be seen that, in our population example, deaths of the group remain at a low average level during youth and maturity, then increase rapidly, generating a peak in mortality, and decrease even more rapidly until they reach zero at the end of the lifespan. This rapid growth and decline in mortality does not occur in the case of the radioactive source, which maintains a slow decline. We can illustrate this difference in trends even more clearly in Figure 3, which shows the two different trends in the mortality risk (or mortality force) μx function (which will be better defined in Section 7).

Fig. 3 - Mortality force function (μx) in a 5-years age interval as the age increases (vertical log. scale)

In humans, the force of mortality μx increases exponentially with age, while in the case of the radioactive source, the risk of decay is constant (remaining equal to the radioactive source decay constant). This figure also highlights a constant and typical feature of human mortality trends: in a logarithmic scale diagram, from the middle age onwards, the growth of the mortality risk function appears roughly as a straight line sloping upwards. This experimental characteristic of mortality statistics was highlighted many years ago by research conducted by the statistician Gompertz and is known as Gompertz's law, Ref. [3]. This law is not derived theoretically, but empirically, and researchers and demographers around the world are challenged to justify the experimental data emerging from this law on a theoretical basis. We will not attempt here to review the vast scientific literature on the subject, but will limit ourselves to illustrating some results recently obtained by the author. In this article, we will illustrate a theoretical model capable of explaining the shape of the mortality peak shown in Figure 3 and thus also of justifying the characteristic of Gompertz's law. To this end, Section 2 will present an abstract cellular automaton, called the Arbitrary Oscillator, that can encounter random death events during its life cycle. In Section 3, the mathematical characteristics of the statistical distribution of death events relating to the Arbitrary Oscillator thus identified will be compared with statistical data derived for various populations around the world. The following Sections will illustrate results that predict future evolution of mortality in the event of unlimited growth in lifespan. Moreover, we will consider the hypotheses of discrete sub-compo-

nents of the mortality peak that may justify the asymmetry of the mortality curves. In the final sections of this article, we will reflect on links with the Gompertz law and on the possibility of extending the model to other species of living beings. The Discussion and Conclusion Section will summarise the results and model implications. All content presented in this work is the result of research conducted by the author, details of which can be found in the References. Our aim in this article is to present the results obtained by summarising the main findings and attempting to highlight their demographic significance and possible interdisciplinary correlations.

2. The Arbitrary Oscillator and its equations

Below, we will refer to some results of the research addressed in Ref [4], to which interested readers are referred for further details on the mathematics. Now, let us imagine that we have an abstract object capable of moving between two fixed positions on a straight line, as shown in Figure 4. Our object can decide whether to remain in its current position or move to the alternative position. The decision to stay still or move will appear arbitrary to an external observer, suggesting its unpredictability. We will call this object an Arbitrary Oscillator (ArbO) to differentiate it from the well-known object studied in classical physics called a harmonic oscillator. The movements of our ArbO are synchronised with a periodic clock. At each tick of this clock, our ArbO makes a decision, and the sequence of decisions will constitute a possible evolutionary path in the object’s life cycle.

Fig. 4 - The Arbitrary Oscillator can move between two fixed positions

To illustrate these decision-making processes schematically, we can refer to Figure 5.

Fig. 5 - ArbO decisions splitting evolution with no-death events and with a death event at step 2, respectively

Looking at Figure 5 on the left and starting from the initial ‘Start’ position (which can be any position on A or B), we see that at each decision step there are two possibilities: to stay still or to move. These possible choices are conventionally represented by two rectangles: the one on the left represents the decision to stay still, while the one on the right represents the decision to change. This applies to each step of our clock. Note that the figures do not represent a spatial diagram of the movements between A and B, but rather a diagram of the possible alternative choices (‘stop’ or ‘go’). Let us now add another random event to our model that is not controlled by our ArbO. This event will consist of the possibility of encountering fatal events as a result of the current decision taken: that is, after deciding whether to stay still or move, our ArbO, in implementing the decision, may encounter an end-of-life event (EoL). Figure 5 on the right highlights the occurrence of this event on the map of possible decisions with a black dot. It can be seen that decisions following those in which the end-of-life event occurred will be prohibited. This is highlighted with a dark colour. The presence of one or more EoL events during the decision-making steps will lead to an overall reduction in the total number of possible paths for our cellular automaton. Note that in our simple model, we do not specify whether EoL events are induced by interactions with the external world in spatial positions A or B, or whether these fatal events occur at a certain point in time due to internal events within ArbO or by the interaction between internal/external status. EoL events may or may not occur in conjunction with a decision being made. It can therefore be seen that the number of free rectangles grows exponentially according to the law 2^i as the decision steps i increase, provided there are no EoL events. If we want to describe these processes mathematically, we can refer to Figure 6, which illustrates a generic recursive ‘feedback’

branching process with termination events. In our ArbO case, the β parameter will be equal to 2 (i.e. the ‘left’ or ‘right’ decision), and at each decision step, there will be a certain number v_i (the ‘white’ rectangles), together with a certain number (zero or more) of m_i events EoL (the black dot in Fig. 5).

Fig. 6 - A general branching process with termination events

The sequence of the number of free cells v_i will be determined by the following equation (1):

$$v_i = 2^i - \sum_{t=1}^i 2^{i-t} m_t \quad (1)$$

From (1), we see that the number of ‘free cells’ depends on past history, i.e. on the particular sequence of events m_i . In principle, the process shown in Fig. 7 could continue indefinitely, but, if we want to bring our analogy closer to more realistic situations, we must impose limitations on the duration of the process, which therefore cannot continue “perpetually”. We must therefore impose the condition that at a certain point the process must end (*Constraint C1*) and that the termination must occur no later than a certain maximum number (imax) of steps of our clock (*Constraint C2*). We also want to study, within the limits set by C1 and C2, all the possible paths that ArbO can take in the presence of a maximum total number of ‘m’ events (*Constraint C3*). Remembering that if $v_i=0$ the process stops, we will therefore impose the following equation:

$$0 = 2^{\text{imax}} - \sum_{t=1}^{\text{imax}} 2^{\text{imax}-t} m_t$$

That is, eliminating 2^{imax} and renaming ‘t’ with ‘i’, we have, due to C1 and C2 Constraints:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\text{imax}} (0.5)^i m_i = 1 \quad m_i \text{ positive or null integers} \quad (2)$$

The constraint condition C3 will also be expressed by the next equation (3), where we introduce a parameter TC (like ‘Total Cases’) which is a positive integer ≥ 2 . This parameter is interesting because it defines the total number of ‘fatal’ cases that can occur in the possible paths followed by our cellular automaton. In other words, for every terminal event “m” on our “board” of possible cases, there will correspond a sequence of cells that have been traversed to reach the terminal cell “m”. This sequence constitutes a characteristic “path” associated with the final terminal cell. From this, we obtain that, given TC as the total number of events “m”, we will also have fixed, as TC, the number of paths associated with those terminal events. Moreover, it can be demonstrated that there is a relationship between TC and imax, i.e. they are linked by the equation: $\text{TC} = \text{imax} + 1$. In other words, once one of the two values is fixed, the other is determined accordingly.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\text{imax}} m_i = \text{TC} \quad \text{with } \text{TC} = \text{imax} + 1 \quad (3)$$

Equations (2) and (3), when TC is assigned a value, define a system of equations in the unknowns m_i , which we will call the S-System. This system is part of the so-called Diophantine equations (named after the ancient mathematician Diophantus) since it uses variables with positive integer or null values. There are no known (at least to the author) direct algebraic solutions to an S-System, but numerical solutions can of course be sought using modern computing methods offered by mathematical application programmes. However, one characteristic of S-Systems is that they always have at least one solution: the so-called trivial one, where $m_1 = 1, m_2 = 1, \dots, m_{\text{imax}-1} = 1, m_{\text{imax}} = 2$. This solution corresponds to the evolution of our ArbO, which at each step

encounters an EoL event and a ‘free’ event and can therefore continue (making the ‘safe’ choice) the repetitive cycle until it reaches the imax clock step, where two fatal events occur, and the life cycle ends. The search for solutions does not completely resolve the range of evolutionary possibilities for our ArbO. In fact, once a solution is known, it does not determine a single evolutionary path, but it can be implemented with different ‘paths’ within the diagram in Figure 6. The solutions, indeed, can be represented on a diagram of the type shown in Figure 6, where a total of TC black dots will be arranged for a total of imax rows. Different paths will thus be identified in which ArbO reaches the EoL condition. Let us look at a simple example to clarify the concepts outlined above. Let TC = 5 and, consequently, imax = 4 with four unknowns. m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4 ; in this case, the S-System takes the form (the first equation obtained by the eq. (2) multiplying by $2^{\text{imax}}=16$):

$$\begin{aligned} 8 m_1 + 4 m_2 + 2 m_3 + m_4 &= 16 \\ m_1 + m_2 + m_3 + m_4 &= 5 \end{aligned}$$

and the possible solutions for this S-System are the following three:

$$\begin{pmatrix} m_1 \rightarrow 0 & m_2 \rightarrow 3 & m_3 \rightarrow 2 & m_4 \rightarrow 0 \\ m_1 \rightarrow 1 & m_2 \rightarrow 0 & m_3 \rightarrow 4 & m_4 \rightarrow 0 \\ m_1 \rightarrow 1 & m_2 \rightarrow 1 & m_3 \rightarrow 1 & m_4 \rightarrow 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

We note that the last solution is the trivial one which, as mentioned above, is always present for every S-System. Returning now to the graphical representation shown in Figure 6, we can apply this representation to each of the three available solutions. If we take, for example, the first solution, it can be represented as shown in Figure 7:

Fig. 7 - The four different instances of the same first solution for an S-System with TC=5

Figure 8 shows that there are four possible representations (or configurations) of the same solution: in all configurations $m_2=3$ e $m_3=2$, as prescribed by the solution considered. However, there are four different situations that ArbO experiences as statistically equivalent to a single solution. We can also note, by observing the graphs in Figure 7, that while there are always five EoL events (black dots), there are also always three ‘safe’ events (white rectangles) after the start: this is a general rule for our S-Systems, namely:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\text{imax}} m_i = \sum_{i=1}^{\text{imax}} v_i + 2 = \text{TC} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) holds for all values of TC and tells us that TC must be greater than or equal to 2, and that for very large values of TC, the total number of type ‘v’ events is practically equal to the total number of type ‘m’ events.

2.1 The ‘most probable’ solution

We have seen in the example in Figure 7 that each solution is associated with a series of configurations in which that solution can be realised. In analogy with the criteria of statistical mechanics applied to the study of atomic phenomena, we will state that the ‘most probable’ distribution of the ‘m’ variables will be the one with the maximum number of configurations (*Constraint C4*) i.e. with the maximum number of ways to realise it. We will try to identify it. For reasons that will be detailed in the following sections, we are interested in studying the behaviour of ArbO, and the relevant solutions paths, when the TC parameter takes on very high values, e.g. TC=100000 or above. In this case, the solution calculation cannot be performed directly using the computer power. For limited values of TC, indeed, these solutions can be calculated numerically by computer. For example, in the case of TC=14, there are 510 solutions, but with TC=21, the number of solutions rises rapidly to 30,410. As TC increases, the number of solutions grows exponentially, and soon the calculation times become so long that the numerical calculation of individual solutions becomes impractical and therefore it becomes impossible to compute and study the whole set of solutions. To search for the ‘most probable’ solution with high TC values, we must therefore resort to different methods. In particular, using Fermi statistics methods -see Ref [5]- we may identify, among the various solutions of an S-System, the one that shows the

maximum number of configurations. This computation has been done by the author in Ref. [4] and, for the reader's convenience, we have included in Appendix an extract of the calculation method used in the work cited in Ref. [4]. The \mathbf{m}_r variables can be calculated as follows in eq. (5) (we use the bold character and the index 'r' to highlight that these \mathbf{m}_r belong to a particular recursive solution):

$$\mathbf{m}_r = \frac{2^r - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} \mathbf{m}_t 2^{r-t}}{2^{-r}(\text{TC} - 2) + 1}; \mathbf{m}_1 = 0; r \geq 2; \quad (5)$$

Solution (5) is therefore the 'most probable' solution and can be calculated recursively. Once a value for TC has been set (usually with $\text{TC} \gg 2$), we start from $\mathbf{m}_1 = 0$ and $r = 2$ and continue by increasing the index r and following the calculation process illustrated in (5). It is interesting to note that once the sequence of variables 'm' has been made known, the sequence of correlated variables 'v' can also be calculated by applying equation (1). These calculations can be performed quickly and easily with the aid of a computer. If we set $\text{TC}=100,000$, for example, we will obtain the following sequence of values (rounded to unity) $\mathbf{m}_r \rightarrow \{0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 3, 10, 40, 155, 572, 1966, 5924, 14315, 24780, 27370, 17537, 6107, 1112, 104, 5, 0, 0, \dots\}$. These values of the variables therefore represent the most probable solution for an ArbO whose TC (Total Cases) parameter is equal to 100,000 fatal cases. If all the values in the above sequence are added together, the total is $100,000+1$, in accordance with equation (3). The sequence also satisfies the condition of equation (2). It can also be noted that the sequence ends rather quickly after 24 steps of our clock, leaving only zero values. This is clearly due to the rapid growth of the values of the "m" variables, which quickly exhaust the target TC values, thus creating a "peak" in the sequence of values that resembles the shape of the curve in Figure 2. It is precisely this apparent similarity in shape to demographic mortality curves that catches our attention and will be discussed in the following Section. Before moving on to this topic, we need to introduce one last mathematical aspect concerning sequences of "m" values: the possibility of expressing these sequences as a continuous function (or rather "distribution") of values. With this formalisation, it will be possible to perform calculations and comparisons with real mortality data more easily, using differential calculus.

2.1.2 The 'continuous' approximation

In reference [4], a 'continuous' approximation of equations (5) was carried out. In practice, this calculation was performed by associating to the recursive process in the equation: $v_{i+1} + m_{i+1} = 2 v_i$ to a differential equation based on the Taylor series expansion, truncated at the first term and adapted to approximate the recursive equation using the parameters 'k' and 'g' for trimming of the results to fit with the discrete distribution. The differential equation is:

$$v' = k(v - m) - g m'; g = \text{const} > 0$$

The parameter k will be easily found to be $k = \text{Log}[2]$ by solving the differential equation in the particular case where $\mathbf{m}=0$ all over the values range.

The above differential equation in two unknown functions m and v can be reduced to a only one unknown $m(r)$ using the following property of the most probable solution already found from the calculation of eq. (5) and recalled in Appendix at equations (24):

$$m/(m + v) = 1 / (1 - 2^{rF-r})$$

Using also the boundary condition:

$$\int_0^\infty m(r) 2^{-r} dr = 1$$

we find a solution representing a possible analytical approximation of the most probable continuous distribution that we call now $m(r, \text{TC})$. It must be noted that the continuous function depicted in equation (6) shows the same constraint features of the discrete 'm' solutions and in particular the area under the curve will be equal to the TC parameter, giving: $\int_0^\infty m(r) dr = \text{TC}$.

$$m(r, \text{TC}) = 2^2 r^{-\frac{(1+2g)\text{Log}(2^{rF} + 2^r g)}{g \text{Log}[2]}} c1 \quad (6)$$

The notation $m(r, \text{TC})$ highlights the dependence of 'm' not only on the variable r (now a real continuous number) but also on the parameter TC, as shown in the following equations, where 'g', 'k' terms are numbers while 'c1' and 'rF' are constants depending only from the TC parameter and 'Log' is the natural logarithm function :

$$\begin{aligned} g &= (1 - k); k = \text{Log}[2] \\ c1 &= (1 + g) (2^{rF} + g)^{1 + \frac{1}{g}} k \\ rF &= \frac{\text{Log}(-2 + \text{TC})}{k} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

3. Comparison between the real demographic data and the $m(r,TC)$ function

3.1 The ‘ergodic’ hypothesis

We now want to verify the possibility of associating the distribution defined in formulas (6) and (7) with the actual demographic mortality distributions found in the demographic LifeTables. To do this, we must first take a step back and return to the diagrams in Figure 7. Here we can see, for a specific solution case, the various paths that a generic single object, called Arbitrary Oscillator, can follow until it reaches an EoL point. In other words, we are representing the possible paths of life and death of a single ArbO object for a specific solution case. In order to extend our reasoning, we must now introduce a kind of ‘ergodic’ hypothesis (with analogy of the systems described in statistical mechanics). We will assume that the various individual configuration paths that ArbO can follow are equally possible and that there is no one configuration that is preferred over the others. (*Constraint C5*). This means that if we now consider the life cycle of a single ArbO, it can end in any of the ways described by the various available configurations. But if we now take at the same time a very large number of ArbO objects, all of which start at the same instant and pursue their life cycle, it seems reasonable to assume that, at the end of the life cycle of this cohort, the most statistically representative implementation of the ArbO life cycle will be the one that corresponds to the maximum number of possible configurations, i.e. the maximum number of ways to implement it, i.e. the most probable solution of the S-System expressed in equations (6) and (7).

The ‘ergodic’ selection

To clarify the reasoning set out above, we can consider the following thought experiment. Let us imagine, once a value of TC has been set, that we print on identical tokens a code that uniquely identifies the various path configurations that ArbO can realise during its life cycle, subject to the mathematical constraints of the S-System. We will therefore have a specific configuration for each token. We also know that, once a solution to S-System has been determined, one or more configurations may correspond to it. Let us therefore colour all the tokens corresponding to a single solution with the same unique colour (in the simple case discussed above, where TC = 5, there are 14 possible configurations: 4, 2 and 8 respectively for the three possible solutions. We will therefore use three different colours to distinguish the 14 tokens). Let us now imagine placing these coded and coloured tokens into a container. If, after shaking the container thoroughly, we draw a token at random, we can say that the probability of drawing a single path/token is the same for all tokens. Conversely, the probability of drawing a particular colour will differ for the various colours/solutions depending on their density within the container. Let us now extend our experiment, imagining that we have N containers, each containing the same number and distribution of our tokens. If we now simultaneously draw a random token from each container, we will have selected N tokens as the result of the experiment. If the number N is sufficiently large, every sample of N selections will always reveal a statistically predominant colour: that of the solution with the greatest number of configurations present. We can therefore conclude that a cohort comprising a large number of ArbOs will always behave statistically in the same way, reflecting the life cycle associated with the most probable solution (i.e. with the maximum number of configurations) described mathematically in equations (6) and (7)

3.2 The correlation with demographic Life Tables

We can now attempt to correlate the curves of our variables ‘m’ with those of the variables ‘dx’ found in the Life Tables like in Fig. 3. To do this, we will consider mortality tables structured 5 x 1, i.e. with age intervals of 5 years referring to survey periods of one year, and we impose the following equation that links the age interval ‘a’ of the 5x1 Life Tables to our time interval ‘r’ in the ArbO life cycle:

$$a = 5 * r \quad (8)$$

This means that if $r = 1$, then $a = 5$ age years; if $r = 2$, then $a = 10$ age years, and so on. By substituting the variable ‘r’ with $(a/5)$ in (6), we will obtain distribution curves on the same age scale as the 5x1 Life Tables. We can also generalise this relationship further by defining it as:

$$a = u * r \quad (9)$$

with ‘u’ considered as a generic time constant which, in the case of humans, we will set equal to 5 years. To visualise the shape of $m(a,TC)$ on the age axis, we will need to choose an arbitrary conventional value of TC, which we will take e.g. as $TC=100000$. Fig. 8 shows the linear and log. plots of the function $m(a,TC)$ (in the following called “mTC”). The mTC values are called ‘dx counts’ for similarity with the Life Tables mortality data. It is also shown the particular ‘a’ value (*apeak*) that leads to the curve maximum (in this case *apeak* ~ 88 years). The mTC curve also shows a slight left asymmetry around the curve peak.

Fig. 8 - Linear and Log plot of the $m(a,TC)$ as function of a , with $TC=100000$

It is interesting to highlight some mathematical properties of these curves (see also Ref. [6]), namely that: 1) there is a relationship between ‘*apeak*’ and TC, which are therefore interdependent, as shown by the following equation (10). This means that, for example, once a TC value has been selected, a specific value for the peak position of the curve is automatically defined, and vice versa.

$$TC = 2 + 2^{-1 + \frac{apeak}{u}} \tag{10}$$

2) For sufficiently high TC values, all mTC curves show the same ‘shape’: as TC increases, the curves expand their areas and shift to the right along the age axis, but do not change in structure. This characteristic can be confirmed by calculating the so-called FWHM (full width at half maximum of the curve), which tends rapidly towards the asymptotic constant value of:

$$FWHM = 15.6228 \text{ age years} \approx 3.12 * u \tag{11}$$

3) As a consequence of this constraint, there is also a maximum height limit for "normalised" curves, i.e. the $mTC(a,TC)/TC$ curves obtained by dividing the curve itself by the value of the current TC parameter, which is also – let us remember – related to its area. This height limit, which will always be less than 1, will have the asymptotic value of:

$$\text{max. normalised curve height} = 0.29254 \tag{12}$$

The availability of normalized ‘mTCn’ curves could be used to evaluate the shape of the various mTCs when distributed over an age range similar to that of the demographic Life Tables, keeping the conventional value of fatal cases at 100,000. To obtain the comparison, it will suffice to multiply the ‘mTCn’ curve by the number 100000. This scale change is carried out in the following Figure 9, which illustrates the different theoretical mortality curves between 15 years and 150 years for ten ‘*apeak*’ values -15 years apart from each other- and with an area (i.e. number of cases) equal to 100,000 over age intervals of five years. The figure shows the constant ‘shape’ and constant maximum height of the various curves after the age of 40.

Fig. 9 - Deaths (dx) as per normalised mTC for 100000 cases and ‘*apeak*’ values 15 years apart

With these conventions defined, we can highlight the correlations sought using a simple graphical method. Figure 10 below illustrates this in detail. We start by using the data from the Life Table for the historical year we want to study. The “dx” data from this table are plotted on a graph (Fig. 10-(a)). Using standard computer interpolation programmes, the points are joined with a continuous line (Fig. 10-(b)). With the mathematical availability of the continuous line, it will be possible to calculate and associate some interesting parameters with the raw data of the Life Table considered, such as the height of the mortality peak, the age at which the peak occurs, and the half-width at full height (FWHM) of the curve itself. Finally, in part (c) of Figure 10, it

will be possible to make the desired association between the actual mortality curve and our mTC of equation (6). In fact, from the age of maximum mortality (“*apeak*”) found in (b), it will be possible to analytically determine the value of TC using equation (10) and then plot (by means of a resizing operation) an mTC curve with the same vertex as curve (b), obtaining Fig. 10 (c). With the two curves identified analytically, it will be possible to integrate them numerically and also determine a percentage coincidence factor between the two areas, specifying the fraction of common area covered by the underlying mTC curve. This % value is shown, for example, in part (c) of Figure 10.

Fig. 10 Demographic mortality data (dots in (a)) are interpolated with a continuous curve (b) and overlaid on an apex compliant mTC curve (c)

3.3. Comparison between the United States, Italy and Japan Life Tables ‘dx’ data and the $m(r,TC)$ function

A large amount of mortality demographic data is available for the various countries and years of collection. We here chose to use the USA, Italy and Japan data. These countries differ in terms of history, geographical location, customs and traditions and population size, and therefore constitute a good test bed for determining statistical invariants despite their differences. It should also be noted that the Japanese and Italian populations have the highest longevity and are therefore useful for studying trends based on this statistical characteristic. The data for Italy and Japan are available at Ref. [7-8]. These data span a 45-year period from 1974 to 2019 (having excluded years after 2019 to avoid statistical peculiar effects due to Covid 19). The USA data were processed from a database of tables made available in the works in Ref. [9] and [10]. The USA data range runs from the year 1900 to the year 2017 mainly in ten years steps, while the Italy and Japan data are available at five years intervals. Due to significant differences in mortality between males and females, gender distinctions have been maintained in the data groupings. This selection of data from the various Life Tables is summarised in Table 1 below.

L. TABLES	1900	1910	1920	1930	1940	1950	1960	1970	1980	1990	2003	2010	2017					
USA	M	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*		*					
	F	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*		*					
JPN	M																	
	F																	
IT	M																	
	F																	
									1974	1979	1984	1989	1994	1999	2004	2009	2014	2019
									*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
									*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
									*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Tab. 1- Selection of mortality data according to period (year) and gender

All these different data sets were subjected to comparison with theoretical predictions of the mTC function using the method described above. This was also done by including in the analysis a graph showing the difference between the actual demographic curve and the theoretical MTC curve; these differential graphs typically show two lobes, one more pronounced on the left and one smaller on the right, in all the situations considered. In the following we provide an example of the graphic evidences obtained. The period figures have been minified to give a quick overview of the evolution of the shape of the curves. Further data are available in Ref. [11].

The USA female data comparison

- The overimposed graphs

— 1900 USA Female — mTC — 1910 USA Female — mTC — 1920 USA Female — mTC — 1930 USA Female — mTC

— 1940 USA Female — mTC — 1950 USA Female — mTC — 1960 USA Female — mTC — 1970 USA Female — mTC

— 1980 USA Female — mTC — 1990 USA Female — mTC — 2003 USA Female — mTC — 2017 USA Female — mTC

- The D-curve graphs

— (1900 - mTC) USA Female — (1910 - mTC) USA Female — (1920 - mTC) USA Female — (1930 - mTC) USA Female

— (1940 - mTC) USA Female — (1950 - mTC) USA Female — (1960 - mTC) USA Female — (1970 - mTC) USA Female

— (1980 - mTC) USA Female — (1990 - mTC) USA Female — (2003 - mTC) USA Female — (2017 - mTC) USA Female

Fig.11 - USA female mortality graphs with poll points, interpolated curve and MTC curve together graphs with the 'difference' curve

4. The conjecture on demographic mortality

Let us now consider the trend shown in the miniaturised graphs in the previous Section. These trends are common to all the charts analysed in the cases set out in Table 1. Firstly, there is a marked decline in infant mortality, which falls as the demographic reference period progresses. The relatively 'flat' section in the middle age groups is also narrowing. Overall, therefore, the curves are narrowing and shifting along the age axis towards older age groups, indicating that mortality peaks occur at a later age. This qualitative trend is clearly evident, as the sampling years progress from one to the next, with all the demographic mortality curves converging towards the shape of the theoretical MTC function. This can also be appreciated visually by observing the progressive reduction in the areas of the right and left lobes of the graphs showing the differences between the two curves. This trend is present, albeit to a greater or lesser extent, in both sexes. Our conjecture on demographic mortality can be summarised in the following statement:

The dx curve of demographic mortality will tend to coincide with the theoretical mTC curve as the longevity of the population under consideration increases.

The above qualitative assessments can be confirmed by numerical measurements of three important parameters: the FWHM, the height of the peak vertex dx, and the difference between the total area covered by the actual curve and the area of the theoretical MTC curve. If the conjecture is credible, then the numerical data should show that the actual peak of the curve will narrow in FWHM and consequently rise, and the area of difference between the two curves will tend to decrease when the longevity of populations increases. The following figures show these trends measured quantitatively. The first figure shows how, as the year of the sampled period increases, the life expectancy parameter 'e0' also increases, indicating an improvement in the longevity of the populations considered (Fig. [12]), in accordance with our assumption. The next figures shows how the FWHM for all cases tends to decrease, approaching the theoretical minimum limit of 15.6 years (Fig. 13). The Figure 14 shows how the height of the mortality peak increases progressively as the peak itself narrows. Finally, the last Figure 15 shows the mismatch ratio ' $(|AL|+|AR|)/AT$ ', where $|AL|$ and $|AR|$ are the absolute values of the areas of the left and right lobes in the difference graphs, and AT is the total area under the actual curve for the case considered. This mismatch tends to decrease, confirming the hypothesized trend.

Fig. 12 - Life expectancy e0 compared to the year of survey for the United States, Italy and Japan, showing an increase in longevity for the three countries

Fig. 13 - The FWHM of the mortality peak for the United States, Italy and Japan showing a trend towards the theoretical minimum limit

Fig. 14 - The mortality peak height for the United States and Italy showing a trend towards the theoretical maximum limit, (Japan data omitted for similarity with Italian data)

Fig. 15 - The area mismatch between real and theoretical curves for the United States, Italy and Japan F., showing a trend to reduction

4.1 A test with regional data

The data highlighted above confirms the credibility of our conjecture. These data, however, consider homogeneous subgroups of both sexes in the various countries considered. The question therefore arises as to whether, within a single country, the conjecture will be valid when restricting the field of analysis to further subgroups, for example, chosen on a regional basis. Counterexamples could therefore emerge that contradict the conjecture by analysing the same groups of males/females distributed across the various regions of a single country. This analysis was carried out for Italy in the year 2019. The following figures illustrate the statistical dispersion of the two parameters FWHM and maximum peak height, according to the various regions into which the population is divided, always considering the female sex (more long-lived). Figures 16 and 17 show that, around the horizontal dotted line marking the average statistical limit for the whole country, the various regional cases (indicated with a distinctive region label) are positioned above or below this limit. However, none of the regional cases exceeds the theoretical limits. Figure 18 shows the “best” region found in approaching the theoretical curve.

Fig. 16 - The FWHM of the mortality peak for the Italian Regions does not fall below the theoretical limit

Fig. 17 - The max. mortality peak height for the Italian Regions does not exceed the theoretical limit

Fig. 18 - The mortality curve of the Marche Region (Italy) corresponds quite closely to the mTC curve (red)

5. An attempt to forecast demographic mortality for the years to come

Considering the above data, there is an almost linear trend in the growth of life expectancy (Fig. 13). This justifies the assumption of a continuous future growth in lifespan (at least for the next decades) and a consequent reduction in the width of the mortality peak. This also allows us to try a forecast for the future evolution of demographic mortality. This can be done by using the mTC function and assuming a future peak linear improvement in continuity with the rate of change recorded in the last years of population surveys. The result of this simulation is shown in Fig. 19 for the case of Italian females. The figure shows the latest demographic curves (2009 and 2019) along with the theoretical projections of the mTC normalized function -multiplied by 100000 - when it assumes a constant shift rate for 'apeak' values for the years ~2030, ~2040, ~2050. These peak values are calculated with the same peak growth rate recorded for last year's survey. It is interesting to note that, as predicted in Section 2, the theoretical mortality curves, while shifting on the age axis, maintain the same shape and height at 29254 deaths (over 100000 total) at the peak mortality.

Fig. 19 - Possible future evolution of demographic mortality according to the conjecture (Italy female case)

Of course, in this hypothetical prediction the demographic curve must also confirm the trend of narrowing left skewness, i.e. we must hypothesize a transition phase from the 'skewed' curves to the final curves. This is shown in the figure with two intermediate curves arbitrarily approaching the theoretical shape. Suppose this last trend were less fast, then the above forecast might be different. This will depend on the speed of reduction of the left skewness. In these hypothetical scenarios, we have assumed a steady increase in life expectancy; however, if this increase were to come to a halt due to an absolute limit on life expectancy, then our mortality curves would stabilise at a maximum peak age, with a mortality curve that remains stable in shape but 'stagnates' in terms of growth across the age spectrum. This hypothesis of 'stagnation' in the growth of longevity can

be justified in the light of our ArbO theory, when we examine equation (10):

$$TC = 2 + 2^{-1 + \frac{apeak}{u}}$$

here we see an exponential dependence of the parameter TC on the value of *apeak*. This means that small increases in the value of *apeak* result in large increases in the value of the TC parameter. Since TC is a parameter that can be correlated with the systemic vital capacity of a generic organism, as we shall see in more detail in Section 8 and in the Conclusions, it therefore seems unlikely that it could grow indefinitely and exponentially in the real world. This would thus lead to a 'saturation' hypothesis for the growth of *apeak* and, consequently, of the growth in longevity. This assumption of saturation is illustrated in Fig. 19 when a maximum lifespan is assumed for the projection furthest into the future.

6. The components of demographic mortality

From the graphs of the real mortality curves analysed so far, in addition to the characteristics already highlighted, one can consider into detail an invariant aspect present -in a more or less accentuated way- in all the real curves: this characteristic is the asymmetry of the mortality curve which shows a 'tail' to the left of the peak and this together with the presence of two other characteristic areas. We can highlight these aspects by observing the following Figure 20.

Fig.20 - Generic mortality curve with Life Table poll points & interpolated curve with A,B,C areas and FWHM line

The figure shows some recurring zones in mortality graphs. These are: zone A, where the effects of infant mortality are evident; zone B, where the mortality counts [dx] are relatively constant and independent of chronological age; and zone C, which is the so-called peak mortality zone. This last zone exhibits the aforementioned peak asymmetry. We saw in Section 3 how the graphs of the difference between the real and theoretical curves always show a lobe to the left of the '*apeak*' that also maintains an invariant shape with an asymmetric tail to the left. This fact makes us wonder whether there isn't a sort of fractal recursion in the structure of these two curves (the main peak and the lobe to its left) and whether -by cyclically repeating the graphical calculation procedure used to highlight these first two peaks- it isn't possible to highlight other cascading 'components' present in the structure of zone C. This analysis was carried out by the author in Ref. [12] and here we report a summary. The following figures show the breakdown of area C into sub-components (Fig. 21). These sub-components are always theoretical mTC functions but with different TC parameters. Three of them are distributed with peaks positioned to the left of the main peak and the fourth largely coincides with the main peak. These four sub-components are sufficient for their sum to coincide with the real points of the Life Table zone C (Fig. 22). The analysis was carried out for all the countries considered above and in all cases, including the gender breakdown, the presence of this division was found. For all cases, four components are sufficient to construct zone C. We can therefore interpret the asymmetry of the real curves as due to different components of the same theoretical curve. The area of three of these components is much smaller than that of the main component, and the areas decrease as one moves away from the main peak, as can be seen in Figure 21 on the right. In the two figures, one can also note a mismatch between the theoretical curve and the last two positions (points) of greatest age in the Life Table. This occurs for the periods and sexes with the highest longevity. In these cases, a tendency for the lobe of the differential curves to contract and become negative is noted. We will return to this aspect later.

Fig.21 - Mortality curve C area split into four components for Italian 2019 females. (Log scale left and linear scale right, dots as per Life Table)

Fig.22 - Mortality curve A and B zones and total sum of C sub-components for Italian 2019 females. (Log scale, dots as per Life Table)

The four peaks are almost equally spaced (between 11-15 years interval) in the age peaks (for females at ~50, ~63, ~77, ~90 ages) for almost all cases/countries considered. This is also shown in Figure 23. These graphs plot the component areas vs the ‘ap’ parameter. It is seen that four clusters of points identify the four components of mortality. This feature - common for the US, Italy and Japan - leads to a similarity in peak shape for the three countries for both males and females.

Fig. 23 - Plot of components areas vs peak ages and poll year for the three countries (female subset)

In the log-scale graphs of Fig. 23, we see a steady shift of the positions of the component peaks age to the right from old to more recent years of demographic sampling, a fact consistent with an improvement in lifespan. These empirical findings can be linked to recent studies, conducted using multi-omics technologies, which have revealed a non-linear trend in biological ageing factors. We will return to this discussion in the concluding Section.

7. Some considerations in relation to Gompertz's law

We saw in the Introduction how Gompertz's law is derived from the analysis of experimental data. It concerns the so-called 'mortality force' or 'mortality hazard' which is conceptually defined by the following equation (13). In practice, $\mu_X[x]$ indicates a sort of instantaneous risk of dying having reached an age 'x'. In the equation $dx[x]$ is the 'distribution' of deaths vs age.

$$\mu_X[x] = \frac{dx[x]}{\int_x^\infty dx[s] ds} \tag{13}$$

Now the law of Gompertz-Markham can be expressed for μ_X (Ref. [13]) as:

$$\mu_X[r] = a + b e^{c \cdot x} \tag{14}$$

Equation (14), with parameters 'a', 'b' and 'c' estimated experimentally, will therefore show an exponential trend, which means a straight-line trend in the case of representation on a logarithmic scale graph (see Fig. 4 previous example). It has also been seen that this law is not only valid empirically for human populations but also appears to be followed in the case of other biological species. Ref [14]. We now have found a mathematical model for the $dx[x]$ distribution, which is precisely our theoretical mTC function. We can then calculate the quantities in formula (13) and see if the result is compatible with Gompertz's law. The result is shown in the following Figure 24 where the μ_X function is represented together with the mTC function (the latter divided by the TC parameter which therefore represents a normalized mortality function). The age intervals can be referred to our 5-years intervals steps, so that e.g. $x = 20$ means age = 100 years. From the graph it can be seen that the theoretical μ_X mortality force function maintains a straight trend in the logarithmic graphic representation for most of the age range, which would confirm the qualitative result obtained from Gompertz's law for this age range. It can therefore be stated that our ArbO model does not contradict but rather confirms the experimental result, at this range level. Two further significant and peculiar aspects can also be noted from the graph: The first is that the two curves of normalized theoretical mortality and mortality force coincide for most of the age range. The second aspect consists of the fact that the mortality force curve tends to saturate and flatten, becoming horizontal in the final period of advanced ages. This last characteristic would make our analysis lean towards the considerations that, in the recent debate among demographers, hypothesize a flattening of the mortality rate at advanced ages (Ref. [15]). This hypothesis is however contradicted by other research on the topic (see Ref. 16). However, we must point out that our analytical model, expressed in the mTC function, while it approximates the real data of the Life Tables well at the peak of mortality, shows limitations in approximating such data at extreme ages (as already noted at the end of Section 5). In this age range, our model may not represent mortality situations realistically. However, if this flattening of the Gompertz curve were confirmed and indeed if it remained at a constant value as in our theoretical calculation, this could mean that, once a certain high age threshold is exceeded, say above 110 - 115 years, we would find ourselves in a condition of mortality risk independent of age but, as in the case of the radioactive source discussed in the Introduction, constant over time.

Fig. 24 - Mortality force (showing a flattening at high ages) and normalized mTC function (TC=100000), with vertical Log. scale

8. A look at other biological species

Up to this point, our analysis has considered demographic data referring to the human species. A question might arise in the reader as to whether the model discussed thus far can be applied to other biological species. In particular, one might ask whether the ageing phenomenon highlighted in the curve in Figure 2 is present in other living beings. Without wishing to make generalizations, we can answer that yes, in many cases, even very biologically diverse ones, the aging phenomenon can be detected. To illustrate this statement we can see the following Figure 25.

Fig. 25 - Survived numbers versus life time (normalized to 1000 newborns) for three species (log. time scale)

The figure shows data from three Life Tables for different biological species: the fruit fly *Drosophila* (laboratory tests as per Ref. [17]), the Dall Mountain Sheep (Ref. [18]) and an example of a human species (Life Table of Japanese females in 2029, Ref.[8]). In all three cases, the phenomenon of ageing (defined as the rapid disappearance of living things after a certain critical age threshold) is evident. This is despite the significant difference in lifespan, which ranges from approximately 100 days to 100 years. In the case of Dall’s sheep, the initial rapid decline was due to “infant mortality” induced by predators in the natural area where the data were collected. If we represent these same data by measuring the deaths over the time interval, we can obtain the following graph in Fig. 26.

Fig. 26 - Number of deaths versus time intervals (normalized to 1000 newborns) for three species (log. time scale)

Here we see - despite the large differences between the species and the times involved - a similar invariant structure appearing for all three cases: the mortality peak in deaths. Recalling the discussion in Section 3.2 and equation (12), and evaluating the FWHM of these mortality peaks, we can estimate what we have called the ‘time constant’ typical of the species, i.e. the parameter ‘u’. This parameter ‘u’ determines the temporal cadence of the statistical ‘ageing’ process in our ArbO model, that is, it tells us how rapidly the development of the time steps brings us closer to the process of exhaustion of the ‘capacity’ of total available cases given by the parameter TC.

	Drosophila	Dall Sheep	Humans
Time constant u	~ 10 days	~ 1 year	~5 years
TC parameter	10-30	~10 ³	~2*10 ⁵

Tab. 2 - Time constant ‘u’ and TC parameter vs three different species

9. A kind of biological ageing clock: the ‘Fermi time’

From what has been said so far, and based on the analogy between the evolution of our cellular automaton and the life cycle of biological organisms, we can introduce the concept of a ‘biological clock’ which – at regular intervals – monitors the organism's state of health. At a certain point in the temporal progression of our clock, critical events with possible fatal outcomes begin to occur and – in the long term – the organism eventually suffers a definitive collapse.

If we go back to the equation that regulates the progress of our ArbO (see also Fig. 6):

$$Q_{r+1} = m_{r+1} + v_{r+1} = 2 v_r$$

we can associate the clock stroke with the recurring parameter ‘r’ and we can interpret the sum of the events ‘v’ and ‘m’ as critical events of a set ‘Q’. The set Q can therefore include events with a “fatal” (‘m’ like ‘mortalis’ in ancient Latin) or “vital” (‘v’ like “vitalis” in ancient Latin) outcome. This set Q has dimensions linked to the parameter TC via the relationship: $Q = 2TC - 2$; we can therefore interpret Q, and consequently the parameter TC, as quantities linked to the ‘fault tolerance’ reserve available to the organism in question: the higher the value of TC, the more likely it is that critical events Q will result – in the early stages of the organism’s life cycle – in safe rather than fatal outcomes. This also explains why the peak mortality *apeak* shifts towards older ages as TC increases. Thanks to the analytical mathematical description recalled in Section 2 and referred to the ‘most probable’ S-System solution, we can study the evolution over time of these quantities as the clock r varies. This evolution is shown in Figure 27.

Fig. 27 - Evolution of m, v, Q events number vs r clock steps for the most probable solution

In the figure (where the usual $TC=100000$ parameter is used as a standard reference) we see that critical Q events begin to appear significantly after a certain number of steps 'r', say after the tenth step. From here on, the growth of critical Q events increases exponentially, even if, in their initial internal distribution, type 'v' events prevail over type 'm' events. Once a certain level of r is exceeded, represented in the figure by a dashed vertical line, where the 'v' events equal the 'm' events, the 'm' events rapidly prevail in the distribution. The process then shuts down due to the disappearance of the 'fuel', i.e., the type 'v' events. This life cycle can also be effectively represented by the following relationship, also depicted in the next Figure 28:

$$m_r / Q_r = \frac{1}{1 + 2^{rF-r}} \quad (15)$$

Fig. 28 - (m_r / Q_r) Logistic shape for $TC = 100000$

In this equation we find a type of statistical distribution well known to researchers and which is called Cumulative Logistic Function and which is found in the description of natural and social processes. In eq. (15) the parameter 'rF' already introduced in the group of equations (7) reappears and now we can understand its meaning. It identifies in fact a particular position of the variable 'r' which is precisely that of the intersection of the two curves 'v' and 'm' or the position in which the ratio m/Q assumes the value of $1/2$. This position is highlighted in the dotted line in the two figures shown above. The reader might ask why we use this particular notation 'rF' and the answer is due to the idea of recalling the analogy with the well known 'Fermi level' used in semiconductors electrons energy bands theory governed by similar equations. Our parameter 'rF' (which we can call the 'Fermi time') is therefore what signals the turning point in the life cycle of our ArbO, as mentioned above. Figure 28 illustrates this evolutionary characteristic. As time passes, critical situations begin to appear in the number of Q. The percentage of fatal events in these situations is minimal initially, but around the value of rF it grows exponentially until it prevails in the final phases and reaches 100% saturation, thus terminating the process itself. We can therefore affirm that our automaton is subjected to an 'ageing' process that arises naturally from the mathematical structure of the equations that describe it and from the hypotheses or constraints on the basis of which these equations were generated. This critical parameter rF is also related solely to the parameter TC via the following relationship already seen in equations (7), where $k = \text{Log}(2)$:

$$rF = \frac{\text{Log}(-2+TC)}{k}$$

10. Discussion and Conclusions

We've seen in the previous sections how there are many possible analogies between the behaviour of the statistical life cycle associated with our abstract object called ArbO and the mortality cycle of living beings, particularly with demographic mortality data. The conjecture presented in Section 4 -namely, that as population longevity increases, the mortality curve will tend to coincide with the theoretical maximum-likelihood curve of ArbO- if assumed to be valid, has led to interesting predictive results, all related to and consistent with the theoretical model of ArbO. Let's briefly review some of these spin-offs of our conjecture.

- It will be possible to associate the real statistical measures of mortality from the Life Tables with a theoretical continuous function that has the same age value as the peak and coincides with the vertex itself. This will allow us to identify a theoretical TC parameter from which other significant properties of the model will then derive.
- Zone A (infant mortality) and Zone B (constant dx) are not foreseen by the ArbO model, therefore, as longevity increases, they will tend to disappear.
- Similarly to the increase in longevity (i.e. the increase in the age of peak mortality) the statistical peak of the 'dx' data of the Life Tables will not be able to narrow indefinitely, but will be limited to a FWHM value equal to $3.12 * u$, where 'u' is the characteristic time constant of the species (in our demographic case assumed to be equal to five years).
- The additionally identified height limit also gives us a quick test for future Life Tables with 5-year age intervals: the 'dx' data for them in the maximum mortality interval may not exceed 29.3 % of the total cases.
- With the availability of a continuous mathematical description of the theoretical mortality curve, it is possible to hypothesize the asymmetric 'tail' to the left of the mortality peak as the result of the presence of four components having the same curve shape, but with different TC parameters. In particular, the four aforementioned components appear on average equally spaced in the age peaks (for females ~50, ~63, ~77, ~90 ages). They are always present for all sample years and in all three countries considered. On this aspect, a correlation with a recent study using a multi-omics approach must be highlighted: in a paper published in August 2024 in the journal Nature Aging (Ref. [19]), researchers highlighted a non-linear disease risk that accumulates with the biological ageing process. "*The analysis revealed consistent nonlinear patterns in molecular markers of aging, with substantial dysregulation occurring at two major periods occurring at approximately 44 years and 60 years of chronological age*" (cit. from Ref. [19]). This study involved a sample of US persons aged 75 years and under. In our present study, we showed the possible existence of discrete components of demographic mortality with age clusters.
- The proposed theoretical model is not based on interpolations of numerical data series or attempts to fit the data themselves. In other words, the model is built on theoretical, not empirical, foundations. In this sense, when compared with Gompertz's empirical law, the model does not contradict it, but rather confirms it within the range of greatest experimental validity of the law itself. The model also contributes to the debate on the slowing of the mortality force, highlighting its saturation at extreme ages, where, however, the statistical data are less reliable and show greater uncertainty.
- The model proposes a single general mortality function that depends only on an absolute parameter TC ("Total cases") and that varies with a time clock 'r' that can be transformed into an age datum 'a' of the modelled subject by using the relation $a = r * u$, where 'u' is the species time constant. This allows the study of Life Tables of different species using the same mathematical framework.
- In the conclusions of Section 5, we also saw that the model we have proposed makes unlimited increases in life expectancy implausible.

The above-listed implications are the most immediate ones of our proposed model. However, a more fundamental correlation must also be considered when analyzing the model's similarities with social aspects. We would like to cite here two fragments of the conclusions reported in the text of our initial research on the model. These considerations are still valid, so we propose them again to the reader. Indeed, "*when we associate an abstract object such as ArbO with real living subjects we can assume direct analogies with e.g. mortality events but less clear, in the analogy, is the meaning of the TC parameter and also of the v and Q variables. For the latter two variables we can give interpretations such as: number of "critical" decisions/events in a time interval (Q variable) and number of "safe-ending" decisions/events in the same interval (v variable)*". And later-on: "*In sociological terms, our TC could represent a generic social target parameter such as 'longevity', whose improvement corresponds to a similar improvement in life expectancy. An example of such 'social' parameter can be the 'Intrinsic Capacity'(IC), a concept introduced by the World Health Organization, in the context of the healthy ageing target. The IC parameter refers to an individual's overall functional reserve, that is, the set of his physical and mental capacities that determine his well-being and autonomy as he ages.*" (Cit. from Ref [4]). Another correlation between the model and recent research is its connection to the nature of ageing. The proposed model does not address the specific mechanism of ageing, that is, whether it is due to degeneration at the basic biological level (cellular and/or DNA) or at the systemic level (e.g. reliability models based on increasing failures in the aging organism as a whole). The model proposed here highlights the statistical nature of the "pressure" to end one's life cycle once a maximum TC limit of critical events has been set, which is approached over time. Naturally, this forced termination of the life

cycle is imposed by the constraints assumed a priori and highlighted throughout our discussion. These constraints are fundamentally based on the assumption that the model's life cycle cannot proceed indefinitely but must terminate under certain mathematically quantified conditions. Furthermore, the ways in which the process terminates are assumed to be equivalent, unpredictable, and without most likely paths. A constant comparison with future Tables of Life will confirm or deny the validity of the proposed model. A possible extension of the model could also be evaluated by moving from the animal to the plant world. The branched structure of many plant species could, in fact, be a potential application for our cellular automaton.

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Appendix (extract from Ref. [4])

There are some formal analogies between the Arbitrary Oscillator model above described and the quantum models studied in the last century by E. Fermi to derive its statistics for ideal gas of molecules and electrons. In both cases we deal with each other indistinguishable objects, that can be arbitrarily allocated into available empty positions over certain predefined levels and imposing only one item per position. In both cases, any possible allocation must comply with some "boundary" conditions. In the next rows we follow the approach of the great scientist even using the same notations and rationale. This Fermi method is well described in his book "Molecules, Crystals and Quantum Statistics", Ref. [5]. The rationale is as follows:

- we seek for the most probable solution of a S^{TC} system
- to achieve this, we consider the number of ways to distribute some m events over the available Q cells at each step level
- the most probable solution will have the maximum number of the above said ways, say Π
- we look for this maximum, looking at the maximum of $\text{Log}(\Pi)$ -that is the same thing- using the method of Lagrange multipliers
- finally, we consider the boundary conditions to fix the unknown parameters

Considering our ArbO model, a generic S^{TC} system, associated to our ArbO, will be governed by the following equations:

$$Q_r = m_r + v_r \quad (16)$$

$$v_r = 2^r - \sum_{t=1}^r 2^{r-t} m_t \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^{Rmax} m_r = TC \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^{Rmax} 2^{-r} m_r = 1 \quad (19)$$

the above said Π value will be:

$$\Pi = \binom{Q_1}{m_1} \binom{Q_2}{m_2} \dots \binom{Q_r}{m_r} \dots$$

where the m_r and, accordingly, the Q_r , are solutions of a S^{TC} system and the symbol $\binom{Q_r}{m_r}$ represents the binomial coefficient. If we pass to the natural logarithms $\text{Log}()$ function and using the Stirling approximation formula, we will have:

$$\text{Log}(\Pi) = \sum_{r=1}^{Rmax} (Q_r \text{Log} Q_r - m_r \text{Log} m_r - (Q_r - m_r) \text{Log} (Q_r - m_r))$$

we now consider the eq. (17), where we extract the m_r term from the \sum symbol, obtaining:

$$v_r = 2^r - m_r - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} 2^{r-t} m_t \quad (20)$$

now, remembering the (16), we have:

$$Q_r = 2^r - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} 2^{r-t} m_t \quad (21)$$

We see that, in the above eq., the Q_r variable is independent from m_r , thing that is reasonable since $Q_r = 2 v_{r-1}$. Now we can move on to the search of the maximum of the $\text{Log}(\Pi)$ searching the maximum of the expression: $\text{Log}(\Pi) - a C1 - b C2$, where a, b are undetermined constant coefficients (according to Lagrange multipliers method), and C1, C2 are the first member of eq. (5) and (7), also constant in total value. We search then for the null condition of the derivative vs m_r of the expression :

$$\text{Log}(\Pi) - a \sum_{r=1}^{Rmax} m_r - b \sum_{r=1}^{Rmax} 2^{-r} m_r \quad (22)$$

After some mathematical steps, we find -as the null condition- the expression

$$m_r = \frac{2^r - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} 2^{r-t} m_t}{1 + e^{a+2^{-r} b}} \quad (23)$$

Recalling the (12) , we have:

$$m_r = \frac{Q_r}{1 + e^{a+2^{-r} b}}$$

To find the values of a and b coefficients, we sum over r and, imposing the boundary conditions (18) and (19) , we obtain, after some algebra, the following expression:

$$m_r = \frac{2^r - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} m_t 2^{r-t}}{2^{-r} (TC - 2) + 1}$$

If we introduce the parameter $rF = \log(TC-2)/\log(2)$, we obtain the following set of equations that represent - in recursive way - the most “probable” solution set of a diophantine S^{TC} system. We use here the bold character to distinguish this particular solution set to the other possible solutions.

$$\begin{aligned} rF &= \frac{\log(TC - 2)}{\log(2)} \\ \mathbf{m}_r &= \frac{2^r - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} \mathbf{m}_t 2^{r-t}}{2^{rF-r} + 1} \\ \mathbf{v}_r &= 2^r - \mathbf{m}_r - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} \mathbf{m}_t 2^{r-t} \\ \mathbf{Q}_r &= 2^r - \sum_{t=1}^{r-1} \mathbf{m}_t 2^{r-t} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$